

Can *Macrolophus pygmaeus* mediate the damage caused by *Bemisia tabaci* on vegetable crops?

Whitefly, Predator, Zoophytophagy, Trophic interactions, Plant morphology

Italy

Today, pest management based mainly on biological control represents the most sustainable alternative to pesticide use. The whitefly *Bemisia tabaci* is one of the key pests negatively impacting the yield and quality of vegetable crops, while the predator *Macrolophus pygmaeus* is one of the main natural enemies widely used for its control, although it can sometimes behave as a pest, causing damage to plants.

This study analyzes *M. pygmaeus*'s role as a plant feeder alongside the whitefly on potted eggplants in lab conditions. Results show no height differences between plants infested solely by the whitefly or by both insects compared to non-infested controls. However, plants infested solely by *B. tabaci* exhibit significant reductions in chlorophyll content, photosynthetic performance, leaf area, and shoot dry weight compared to those infested by both the pest and its predator or non-infested controls. Conversely, root area and dry weight experience greater reductions in plants exposed to both insects compared to those infested only by the whitefly or non-infested plants. These findings emphasize *M. pygmaeus*'s significant role in mitigating *B. tabaci* damage to host plants, suggesting early release in greenhouse settings during infestations.

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<https://www.mdpi.com/2075-4450/14/2/164>

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>>> PRACTICE ABSTRACT 7 <<<

Early warning system and mitigation strategies for Tomato brown rugose fruit virus

ToBRFV, Early warning system, Mitigation strategies, Commercial tomato cultivation

Belgium and Netherlands

Tomato brown rugose fruit virus (ToBRFV) poses a huge threat to commercial tomato cultivation worldwide. Due to its high persistence and easy mechanical transmission, *ToBRFV* is extremely hard to get rid of once it enters the greenhouse. Current management strategies therefore centre around preventive measures, such as improved hygiene, in an attempt to keep the virus out of the crop. **Early detection of the virus** can also play an important role. Our research shows that *ToBRFV* circulates in greenhouse water systems and can be detected in drain water samples before the plants start showing symptoms. We illustrate that drain water can be used to monitor *ToBRFV* outbreaks and thus can serve as an early warning system.

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<https://zenodo.org/records/7928630>

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OPTIMIZATION OF SOLARIZATION AND STREAMING METHODS TO ERADICATION TMV

Tecnova, Landwirtschaftskammer Nordrhein-Westfalen (LNW), Solarization, Steam Treatment, PCR (Polymarase Chain Reaction).

Spain

TECNOVA (TEC, Spain) and **Landwirtschaftskammer Nordrhein-Westfalen (LNW, Germany)** work together in the task "**Optimization of eradication methods after tobamovirus outbreaks**" of **VIRTIGATION** project. Both institutes are working on the validation of **solarization and steaming** methods to eradicate tobamoviruses in **contaminated cocopeat** bags by **TMV (Tobacco mosaic virus)**.

Solarization Method

For **solarization**, **TEC** utilized a transparent **37.5 um thick** polyethylene plastic for **60 days** (from **September** to **November** to simulate the summer in other European countries) with temperatures ranging from **15.2 to 46.2°C**. The results of **solarization** have been very promising. All tomato plants grew symptom-free in **solarized** bags. Only in one of the six lines (temperature > **40°C** during **10-13 days**) were viruses detected by **PCR**. Moreover, in bags with infected material (roots and leaves), the maximum temperature was up to **4°C** higher than in bags with just substrate.

Steaming Protocol

LNW is testing two **steaming** protocols: (1) **90°C for 20 min** and (2) **90°C for 40 min**. The steaming results are forthcoming. After **steaming**, it has been observed that: (i) plants in the non-steamed bags showed better fitness than the steamed variants; (ii) growth of mold and fungi could be observed on the substrate; and (iii) substrate bags must be used immediately and cannot be stored for a while.

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Presented in: Symposium soils disinfection, Almería, June 2022

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Exploring wild *Solanum* germplasm for resistance to ToBRFV (Tomato Brown Rugose Fruit Virus)

ToBRFV (Tomato Brown Rugose, Fruit Virus, Wild *Solanum* germplasm, Resistance, Tomato production

Netherlands

ToBRFV is a newly emerged virus that causes severe losses in tomato production. Within five years, **ToBRFV infections** have been reported in Asia, North America, and Europe. ToBRFV belongs to the tobamovirus genus; however, all the available tomato-resistant varieties used for tobamoviruses, such as TMV and ToMV, cannot halt infections caused by this new virus.

The severity of this disease, its rapid spread, and the scarcity of resistant cultivars make ToBRFV a global threat to tomato production. Our objective is to find **ToBRFV resistance** in wild *Solanum* accessions and introgress this trait into tomato cultivars, reaching the first step for creating modern resistant tomato varieties.

So far, we have screened 75 *Solanum* accessions, from which two ***S. pennellii*** were found resistant to ToBRFV. **Segregation populations** have been obtained from these two accessions, which is the first step for mapping the gene responsible for the resistance trait. The **identification** and **introgression** of the resistance gene are in progress.

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Presented in: XVII SOLANACEAE2022

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CHARACTERIZATION OF TOMATO LEAF CURL NEW DELHI VIRUS INFECTING CUCURBITS IN FRANCE

Tomato leaf curl New Delhi virus (ToLCNDV), Mediterranean Basin, Bemisia tabaci, Disease management

France

Tomato leaf curl New Delhi virus (ToLCNDV) is emerging in the Mediterranean Basin, starting from Spain in 2012. First observed in France in 2020 in Gard and Bouches-du-Rhône. Mediterranean ToLCNDV, a bipartite begomovirus, primarily affects zucchini and other cucurbits, genetically distinct from Asian (Indian)-ToLCNDV with a broader host range.

The cryptic species of whitefly *Bemisia tabaci* is the main insect vector of *ToLCNDV* while mechanical inoculation is also possible. Previous studies indicate that the Mediterranean clade represents a homogenous population, probably originating from a single introduction.

We established a suitable protocol of inoculation and performed biological and molecular characterization of the French isolates in order to estimate their risks of emergence and their potential agronomic impact. Symptom observation of French *ToLCNDV* isolates on melon and zucchini showed two different types so-called "severe" and "recovery".

French *ToLCNDV* is transmitted by *Bemisia tabaci* but not by *Trialeurodes vaporariorum*. Experimental analysis indicates the susceptibility of Bryony and Tomato to *ToLCNDV* from France and Spain, possibly serving as virus reservoirs. Our findings advance understanding and guide future disease management.

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Presented in: ISPVE 2022 and Rencontres de Virologie Végétale RVV2023

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